

OpenRiskNet

RISK ASSESSMENT E-INFRASTRUCTURE

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Report on the results of the
Implementation Challenge

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OpenRiskNet: Open e-Infrastructure to Support Data Sharing, Knowledge
Integration and *in silico* Analysis and Modelling in Risk Assessment

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www.openrisknet.org

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Table of Contents

SUMMARY	5
INTRODUCTION	6
PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATION	7
Implementation challenge application procedure	7
Implementation challenge winners	9
Technical and administrative implementation of the Implementation Challenge	14
Description of services	17
The Adverse Outcome Pathway Database (AOP-DB)	18
Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database	19
Nano-QSAR to predict cytotoxicity of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles	20
ToxPlanet database	22
OCHEM models	23
FAME 3 site-of-metabolism predictor	24
Prosilico's Human In Vivo ADME/PK-Prediction Studio	25
Nanoinformatics Tool for the Virtual Screening of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles via Enalos Platform	26
nanoQSAR model for the prediction of the cellular uptake and the virtual screening of nanoparticles via Enalos Platform	28
PySquonk	30
ToxicoDB	32
ToxTargetLinks	33
Participation of the associate partners at the final OpenRiskNet workshop	34
CONCLUSION	35
GLOSSARY	36
REFERENCES	37
ANNEXES	38
Annex 1. Application form to the implementation challenge	38

SUMMARY

The Implementation Challenge was created to select external tools and services, especially in areas of risk assessment, not completely covered by the OpenRiskNet consortium, to be prioritised for their integration into the e-infrastructure. Third parties could apply for financial and technical support offered by OpenRiskNet partners. The selection was made by the scientific advisory board. The winners were asked to become an OpenRiskNet associated partner¹. The selection criteria included the tools which were complementary to the tools from within the consortium, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL), availability of APIs and other technical requirements. In total, 14 applications (20 tools or services) were received, while 10 applications (12 tools or services) were awarded and entered in the associated programme and the implementation process.

The services integrated cover data and knowledge sources as well as different software tools across all areas of risk assessment. The specific services were 1) the Adverse Outcome Pathway Database (AOP-DB), 2) Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database, 3) Nano-QSAR to predict cytotoxicity of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, 4) ToxPlanet database, 5) OCHEM models, 6) FAME 3 site-of-metabolism predictor, 7) Prosilico's Human In Vivo ADME/PK-Prediction Studio, 8) Nanoinformatics Tool for the Virtual Screening of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles via Enalos Platform, 9) nanoQSAR model for the prediction of the cellular uptake and the virtual screening of nanoparticles via Enalos Platform, 10) PySquonk, 11) ToxicDB and 12) ToxTargetLinks.

¹ <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/implementation-challenge/>

INTRODUCTION

To ensure the usability of the OpenRisknet e-infrastructure, alignment with the community as well as to pursue complete coverage of important tools, a network of partners was established and organised into the Associated Partners Programme² [1]. This programme aims at strengthening the working ties between the OpenRiskNet Consortium members and these associated partners by including them in the decision making process on selecting technical solutions for the infrastructure components and prioritizing services to be integrated, to give feedback on and contribute to the developments and case study work, and foster collaborative developments between consortium and associated partners. The three different types of users include:

1. Service providers, who would like to integrate their databases and software tools into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure;
2. Early adopters, who would like to use the infrastructure for their predictive toxicology and risk assessment tasks and as such provide feedback on their experiences and demonstration showcases of the services and functions provided by the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure; and
3. Technology partners, who provide hardware and software solutions adopted by OpenRiskNet and are willing to give technical support.

While the main interaction with the members of the Associated Partner Programme was through personal meetings and discussions, information sharing was established for key pieces of information (including confidential information) like source code, surveys and interviews, technical and user support, etc. The Implementation Challenge was also established to provide financial support for service integration carried out by the Service Provider users.

The Implementation Challenge was created to select external tools, especially in areas of risk assessment, not completely covered by the OpenRiskNet consortium to be prioritised for their integration into the e-infrastructure. Third parties could apply for financial and technical support offered by OpenRiskNet partners. From 14 applications, 10 institutions, called Implementation Challenge Winners in the following, with overall 15 databases or software tools were selected by the Scientific Advisory Board as highly relevant for OpenRiskNet and complementary to other tools and funded by the Implementation Challenge with a total budget of approximately 100,000 €. From these, 12 could be integrated in OpenRiskNet during the time of the project. For the other 3 tools, a clear roadmap for the implementation was developed, the first implementation steps were executed and the winners will continue the implementation in the near future.

² <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/>

PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation challenge application procedure

Application was open to any organisation such as a university, institute, consortium, non-governmental organisation (NGO), a small or medium enterprise (SME) or a large commercial entity. Individuals could not be supported because of the EU regulations for in-kind work (more details are given in the “Technical and administrative implementation of the Implementation Challenge” section below). The challenge was advertised on the website, on social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, etc.), different relevant mailing lists and announced at conferences and workshops in the form of fliers, parts of posters and slides during talks. Applicants were directed to a web form (Google forms) to provide the requested information on the proposed services and submit their application at any time. For the selection, three cut-off periods were established: 31 October 2018, 31 January 2019 and 30 April 2019.

The application consisted of a description of the services (*up to five per Organisation*), that referred to the categorisation into a specific risk assessment area and detailed on:

- How the service will profit from OpenRiskNet and specifically from combining it with other OpenRiskNet services;
- How will other services or the core infrastructure profit from the integration of the new service;
- To which OpenRiskNet case studies the service could be applied;
- If the service be used directly by scientists, risk assessors or regulators or will it support the core infrastructure by providing features to multiple services.

Also, the service had to be identified e.g. main contact person, URLs, publications on the service, current status, targeted users and license type (the complete form can be found in **Annex 1**). To guide the applicants, the following selection criteria were formulated and clearly communicated on the Implementation Challenge webpage:

- **Complementarity with OpenRiskNet services:**
 - Less covered areas of the risk assessment framework;
 - Combinable with data and tools already available or planned to be integrated (e.g. uses input provided by ORN partners)
- Relatively high **TRL** preferable with **existing APIs**;
- **Adding requirements** for the infrastructure, e.g.:
 - High or highly varying demand of computer resources;
 - Complex workflow linking different tools;
 - Need to access commercial license.

Besides relevance to the scientific community and OpenRiskNet stakeholders and scientific integrity, one of the most important criteria was the technical readiness level, since the funds aimed to cover the effort needed for making the service OpenRiskNet-compliant and deployable/accessible in virtual environment (VE) but not the development or improvement of the service *per se*. As for services provided by OpenRiskNet consortium members, work to achieve this compliance can be grouped in

eight areas, from which the most beneficial for a specific service were identified and executed by either the associated partner (mainly area 1-5) or consortium member supporting the Implementation Challenge (mainly area 5-8 and technical support to the earlier areas):

1. Utilising the OpenRiskNet APIs to ensure that each service is accessible to our proposed interoperability layer;
2. Annotating the services according to the semantic interoperability layer concept using defined ontologies;
3. Containerising the services for easy deployment in virtual environments of OpenRiskNet instances;
4. Documenting the scientific and technical background;
5. Deploying the service into the OpenRiskNet reference environment;
6. Listing the service in the OpenRiskNet discovery services;
7. Listing in other central repositories like eInfraCentral, bio.tools and TeSS (ELIXIR);
8. Providing legal and ethical statements on how the service can be used.

To make the selection process as transparent as possible and avoid bias from the consortium members on the selection, the decision on the winning tools and organisations was completely put into the hands of the OpenRiskNet Scientific Advisory Board (SAB). All information from the applicants was sent to the advisors and voting was performed also via a Google web form. After the first application period, the OpenRiskNet coordination team asked the advisors for feedback on the selection procedure. This showed that some of the services were negatively evaluated because the information provided by the applicants was not sufficient. This issue was addressed by improving and extending the guiding text for each question in the web form, explaining in more detail what information should be provided. We then also encouraged the failing applicants to resubmit their proposals with additional information added. This was employed by one application, who was then successful in the second round of applications. In general, the improved guiding text, as well as support to applications from the consortium members with respect to eligibility and linking to existing services even before the application, resulted in a 100% success rate in round 2 and 3, although the number of additional winners needed to be limited to be able to provide the optimal support by the consortium members.

All applicants were informed by the coordinator about the results. Any comments resulting from the discussions between the reviewers and conveyed to the coordinator, were also sent to the applicants. A partner from the consortium was selected for individual winners as a first contact point for scientific and technical questions. This person escalated these questions to the relevant consortium members and monitored the timeliness of follow-ups, organised meetings in larger groups when required, evaluated the relevance of the tools for case studies and brought the winners in contact with the relevant case study leaders. Besides this scientific management, the contact partner also helped to organise the legal and administrative tasks like development of a work plan and an associated budget, contract negotiations and reporting were then executed by Edelweiss Connect as the coordinator, following a protocol described below in the “Technical and administrative implementation of the Implementation Challenge” section.

Implementation challenge winners

In total, **14 applications (20 databases and software tools)** were received over all three cut-off periods, one of these being a resubmission. From these, **10 winners** (representing **12 databases and software tools**)³ were selected by the Scientific Advisory board and awarded and then entered in the Associated Partner Programme⁴ and the implementation process. The numbers per period are:

- Period 1 (before 31 October 2018): 10 application, 6 funded
- Period 2 (1 November 2018 to 31 January 2019): 2 applications, 2 funded
- Period 3 (1 February 2019 to 30 April 2019): 2 applications, 2 funded

In the following, we present some general observations on the applications and winning services. More details on the winners, the implemented services and the interactions with OpenRiskNet especially in respect to the case studies are presented in the “Description of services” section below as well as in Deliverable Reports D1.5 “Finalization of case studies and analysis of remaining weaknesses” and D4.4 “Report of the Service Integration with OpenRiskNet (Final Report)”.

The first round clearly showed the largest amount of applications demonstrating the success of the dissemination activities to make OpenRiskNet and specifically the Implementation Challenge known in the scientific community. In the second and third application period, a more focused advertising strategy was followed to keep the number of winners at a level, at which the consortium was still able to provide the financial but even more important strong technical support, and still be able to complement the areas covered by the services of OpenRiskNet and even expand the user group to neighbouring areas like rare diseases (European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases represented by Leiden University) and fragment screening (represented by the Diamond Light Source and its users). On the one hand, the two examples just mentioned, together with the University Health Network, Toronto, Canada, the US EPA, and the Korean Institute of Toxicology (KIT) demonstrate that, even if specific services of the winning institutions were supported by the Implementation Challenge, users addressed and profiting by the collaborations of OpenRiskNet with the winners are in many cases not individuals but larger (sub-)communities like the users of Diamond Light Source or the complete EJP on Rare Diseases, other consortia like the University Health Network or stakeholder groups like risk assessors profiting from the easier access to the knowledge stored in the AOP-DB or collected by KIT.

On the other hand, there was also an encouraging number of applications from international SMEs (see **Figure 1**). Five applications (36 %) came from SMEs, from which four (40 % of all winners) were funded. Since the 5th application was a re-submission, the final success rate for SMEs was 100%. This shows that there is high interest in companies providing highly sophisticated data sources and modelling tools to industry, risk assessors and regulators, to provide commercial services in a harmonised and interoperable fashion on an open, community-driven e-infrastructure. Diamond Light Source can also be put into this category since, even if we list it as a research institute, it is also a commercial entity. Working with these partners and understanding their requirements and reasons to join was of extreme importance to develop the sustainability and exploitation plans in which funding for maintenance and further development of the infrastructure comes, at least in parts, from commercial revenue but also added complexity to the developed

³ <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/implementation-challenge/>

⁴ <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/>

solutions caused by the need to handle licenses and protect confidential, commercially relevant information and data.

The other applications were distributed more or less equally between universities and research institutes/governmental agencies. It was especially encouraging that US EPA and KIT could be attracted to a programme clearly design for service providers since they have a clear commitment to provide services for risk assessors and regulators identified as one important end user group of OpenRiskNet. The distribution of funded institutions very closely follows the distribution of the applications (**Figures 1 and 2**) demonstrating that there was no bias for or against one of the groups and that criteria of (i) scientific excellence, potentially favoring academic institutions, and (ii) technology readiness, potential favoring commercial entities, were considered equally important.

Figure 1. Distribution of types of institutions in Implementation Challenge applications

Figure 2. Distribution of types of institutions in Implementation Challenge winners

The equal distribution between commercial and public institutions can also be seen by the

licence types used for the provided tools, with equal share between open source and commercial licenses with a very small number of freeware (see **Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Distribution of types of licences of services proposed to the Implementation Challenge

Next, we will have a look at the demographic coverage. The applications came from eleven different countries world-wide with the four non-EU countries (Brazil, Canada, Korea and the USA) (see **Figure 4**). Only two countries have more than one applications: USA (both funded) and UK (one funded, one not funded).

Figure 4. Demographic distribution of Implementation Challenge applicants

As mentioned above, one main criterion for the selection was the technological readiness. **Figure 5** shows some important properties of the services before the start of the OpenRiskNet integration. Three of them, availability as web server, availability of application programming interfaces and containerization, are directly relevant to the tasks of the implementation challenge. More than 60% were already available as web services and, in this way, offered a very good starting point for the integration. For the remaining, it was checked if services from OpenRiskNet consortium members could be reused directly

or could be taken as a template for the development. For example, the two services from KIT could be realised using the data management solution from Edelweiss Connect and the Jaqpot modelling tool from NTUA. AOP-DB from US EPA was made available following the concepts developed for AOPwiki and WikiPathways by UM. APIs and containerisation were less well covered and were main tasks for many Implementation Challenge projects. The final property shown in **Figure 5** is the availability of a graphical user interface and this was available for more than 60% of the services. This is very important for the easy access of the tools provided to the end users. This focus on end users can also be seen in **Figures 7 and 8**, with more than 85% of the applicants categorising their services as targeting end users. However, we expect that the Implementation Challenge will change this in the midterm. Even if the graphical user interface is in most cases also available on the reference environment and can be deployed in other virtual environments, the work during the Implementation Challenge concentrated on the API developments to make the services interoperable with other services and accessible from the different workflow management tools. In this way, the services will become more attractive to developers since they can create advanced workflows and applications reusing functionality of different OpenRiskNet services including the Implementation Challenge projects. Finally, **Figure 8** shows the toxicology and risk assessment areas covered by the services proposed for the Implementation challenge. All areas are covered reasonably and build a good complementarity to the services provided by the OpenRiskNet consortium.

Figure 5. Implementation status of services proposed to the Implementation Challenge

Figure 6. General categories of target audience for services proposed to the Implementation Challenge as specified by the providers

Targeted users (2)

14 responses

Figure 7. Stakeholder groups identified as target users for services proposed to the Implementation Challenge as specified by the providers

Count of Risk assessment area

Figure 8. Risk assessment areas covered by the services proposed to the Implementation Challenge as specified by the providers

Technical and administrative implementation of the Implementation Challenge

To organise the technical realisation of the Implementation Challenge project, a contact person was assigned to each winner. This person guided the winner through a procedure to collect all information and requirements for the specific project following this workflow:

- 1) Analysis of the database or software tool to identify the steps needed for the integration into OpenRiskNet;
- 2) Identification of additional consortium partners needed to support the implementation;
- 3) Prioritisation of tools if multiple were submitted by the winner in the application;
- 4) Prioritisation of the implementation steps;
- 5) Identification of existing OpenRiskNet tools to support the integration especially relevant if the tool was not available as a web service before the start of the programme;
- 6) Listing of support efforts, which need to be provided by the consortium;
- 7) Generation of a work plan based on the previously collected knowledge, anticipated length of the project and available manpower at the winning institution and supporting consortium partners;
- 8) Negotiation about the requested budget including personnel and travel allowances for face-to-face meetings between the winner and consortium partners as well as to the final workshop;
- 9) Identification of relevant case studies and OpenRiskNet data and tools to demonstrate interoperability; and
- 10) Start and monitoring of the implementation and the support actions.

In most cases, the implementations were performed at the premise of the winner and the support was mainly provided through virtual meetings and the OpenRiskNet help channels and support infrastructure. However, since many technical details were discussed by the consortium in the Slack messaging application and WP/Case study meetings, the winners were also invited to join the OpenRiskNet Slack workspace and the project internal meetings. In other cases, even more direct interactions and visits to the consortium partners were organised, which are exemplarily highlighted in the following.

For the AOP-DB, one of the winners of the first round of the Implementation Challenge, an employee of the US EPA, has visited Maastricht for 3 weeks to work together with the project partner UM. This temporary exchange allowed for direct face-to-face collaboration within the same office, leading to rapid developments in the service development by having direct guidance and feedback as opposed to collaborating virtually across the atlantic ocean. The AOPLink case study demonstrated the very intensive linking between the AOP-DB and the tools provided by UM, like the AOPWiki and WikiPathways, which also share technology and annotation approaches and allowed for the first public release of AOP-DB.

Another example of very intensive interactions between an Implementation Challenge winner and an OpenRiskNet partner is Diamond Light Source and IM, which was based on an early and continuous dissemination of the OpenRiskNet goals and achievements. After expressing interest already during the proposal stage and becoming the first associated partner, IM had been assisting Diamond Light Source in the early stages of the project in

setting up an OpenRiskNet Virtual Environment (VE) on their in-house cloud infrastructure for their fragment screening follow up workflows. Researchers at Diamond Light Source then saw the Implementation Challenge as an opportunity to achieve better integration between their own tools and other services running in that VE and proposed the development of a library for accessing their Squonk workflows from other OpenRiskNet applications. The implementation of this library was performed by a programmer brought into the IM to profit from first-hand assistance.

While the technical realisation of the programme ran very smoothly and was able to attract high profile associated partners and integrate 12 new services, the administrative implementation encountered more issues. In the project proposal, a specific budget was allocated for the Implementation Challenge distributed between the three consortium partners EwC, UoB and UM. During the negotiation of the Grant Agreement with the EC, it became clear that the transfer of budget to the Implementation Challenge winners is only possible if the budget is specified to be for in-kind work since subcontracting is only allowed to third parties already known at this stage. The latter was not an option since it would have erased the possibility to achieve the main goal of the Implementation Challenge, i.e., to select winners based on their complementarity to existing OpenRiskNet tools throughout the project.

On this basis, the winners were distributed between the three consortium members with in-kind budget and negotiations were started. Immediately it became clear that there is almost no expertise for such contracts for in-kind work at the consortium members and also winner organisations. To optimise the use of resources to develop the contracts and monitoring processes and to bundle all information at one place, the consortium decided that all interactions with the winners with respect to administrative, legal and reporting issues will be handled by the project coordinator, including the management of the complete in-kind budget. After consultation with the Project and Financial Officers, as well as feedback from an auditor hired by EwC, standard contracts were drafted in the form of secondment agreements, where the winning institution seconds one of its employees to EwC for the time specified in the work plan. Such a construct was accepted by the winning institutions in all (except one case) and the contracts were signed with only minor changes to clarify IP rights and publication of the results. The only exception was Diamond Light Source. Even though they proposed the tool to be integrated based on their expertise, the needed knowhow to perform the implementation was not available at Diamond Light Source. Instead the partner IM was commissioned to work on the Implementation Challenge and the secondment agreement was signed directly between IM and EwC. A person with the needed experience was searched and employed by IM for the time of the project.

In summary, centralising all responsibilities of the administrative implementation with EwC brought many advantages:

- The overhead for acquiring the needed expertise to design, draft and negotiate the secondment agreement was reduced since only one version of the standard contract was needed and not three, one for each of the partners to whom in-kind budget was allocated originally;
- All winning institutions were treated equally with respect to the details in the contracts, monitoring and reporting obligations and only one system for reporting as to be set up streamlining the process and optimising the spending of the budget;
- Transfer of money was reduced since the payment went directly to the winners

- after issuing an invoice and not first to UM or UoB and then to the winners;
- With the slimmer decision structure at an SME like EwC, it was possible to react flexible on situations like the one with Diamond Light Source described above;
 - Other small uncertainties like handling of value-added tax were not relevant or could be clarified easily.

Description of services

Table 1 provides an overview of all the services selected for funding by the Scientific Advisory Board, including the winning institution, the application cut-off period, the name of the service and the contact partner from the OpenRiskNet consortium. Some of the winning institutions included multiple services in their applications. Due to the amount of technical support required from the consortium and its relatively small size, not all of the services could be fully implemented but at least one service per winning institution is integrated and available on the reference instance, while for the others the foundation for the implementation was laid and a roadmap developed for executing the following implementation steps continue after the end of the project.

Table 1. Implementation Challenge winners

Challenge Session	Organisation	Contact Person	Technical contact in OpenRiskNet	Service	Description in Service Catalogue
31 October 2018	Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessment, US Environmental Protection Agency	Holly Mortensen	UM	The Adverse Outcome Pathway Database (AOP-DB)	✓
	Korea Institute of Toxicology	Hyun Kil Shin	EwC	Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database	✓
				Nano-QSAR to predict cytotoxicity of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles	✓
	ToxPlanet	Matthias Timberlake	UM/EwC	ToxPlanet database	✓
BIGCHEM GmbH	Igor Tetko	JGU	QCHEM models : prediction of physico-chemical, biological and toxicity endpoints	✓	
15 July 2019	Hamburger Informatik Technologie-Center e.V. (HITeC)	Johannes Kirchmair	VU	FAME 3 site-of-metabolism predictor	✓
31 January 2019	Prosilico	Urban Fagerholm	UU	Prosilico Human Clinical ADME/PK-Studio	✓
	NovaMechanics Ltd	Antreas Afantitis	NTUA	Nanoinformatics Tool for the Virtual Screening of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles via Enalos Platform	✓
				nanoQSAR model for the prediction of the cellular uptake and the virtual screening of nanoparticles via Enalos Platform	✓
Diamond Light Source Ltd.	Rachael Skyner, Frank von Delft	IM	PySquonk	✓	
30 April 2019	Princess Margaret Bioinformatics and Computational Genomics Laboratory, University Health Network, Toronto, Canada	Benjamin Haibe-Kains	UM	ToxicoDB	✓
	Leiden University	Katy Wolstencroft	UM	ToxTargetLinks	✓

The Adverse Outcome Pathway Database (AOP-DB)

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/147/>

Functionality of service

Prior to the Implementation Challenge, the EPA Adverse Outcome Pathway Database (AOP-DB) was an internal EPA SQL database that supports discovery and development of putative and potential AOPs. The AOP-DB aggregates relationships between AOP-gene targets, chemical, disease, tissue, pathway, species orthology information, ontologies and gene interactions to characterise the impacts of chemicals to human health and the environment. The AOP-DB serves as a hypothesis generation and decision support tool for case study development. Associations are sourced from public annotation to provide biological context and are integrated with AOP information centralised in the AOWiki. The AOP-DB allows for fast, automatic AOP profiling and exploration that gives a broad, systems-level overview of the biological context of AOPs, thus dramatically expediting predictive toxicology efforts. The long-term significance and impact of the AOP-DB tool is the continued translation of AOP biological context, and the ability to associate these data between and across AOPs, and with assay, chemical, and disease endpoints [2,3].

Implementation details

The AOP-DB was made available through the OpenRiskNet e-Infrastructure by converting parts of the existing SQL database into RDF, extending the AOPWiki RDF already developed by the hosting OpenRiskNet partner (UM). AOP-DB SQL tables containing data of interest were selected for conversion to RDF. Equipped with additional semantic annotations and object types, the AOP-DB RDF was exposed in a Virtuoso SPARQL endpoint service on the OpenRiskNet platform.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

This implementation challenge was executed in close collaboration with the OpenRiskNet partner UM, who lead the AOPLink case study, and provided technical direction to the EPA partner. As described above, this was achieved in a three weeks stay of a US EPA employee at UM.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The AOP-DB RDF exposed in the SPARQL endpoint service is a direct extension of the existing AOPWiki RDF, which plays a central role in the **AOPLink** case study, and is therefore perfectly integrated with the AOPWiki SPARQL endpoint using consistent vocabulary and identifiers for genes. Furthermore, the AOP-DB SPARQL endpoint is used in a range of workflows, one of which was presented during the final OpenRiskNet workshop⁵, integrated with several of the OpenRiskNet services.

⁵

<https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/workshop/blob/master/Workflows-tutorial/AOPLink%20%2B%20DataCure%20workflow.ipynb>

Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/161/>

Functionality of service

Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database was prepared manually by reading research articles that have performed assays according to OECD and US EPA test guidelines.

Among ecotoxicity assays, Daphnia magna was one of the species that have been assayed most. However, assay results were heterogeneous from study to study particularly for nano materials. Therefore, this data set was compiled for meta-analysis to figure out the major cause of data inconsistency between assays reported in the articles.

Since it was aimed to search certain conditions that may interfere with the assay outcomes, this database includes physicochemical properties of nanomaterials, experimental conditions of assays, and toxic response measurements.

Implementation details

“Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database” was first published as supplementary .csv data file attached to the *"Meta-analysis of Daphnia magna nanotoxicity experiments in accordance with test guidelines"*, a study paper of Korea Institute of Toxicology (KIT) [4].

This data was integrated into OpenRiskNet by uploading it to the EdelweissData solution provided by EwCl. The authors from KIT provided the raw “original_daphnia” data file, the eight derived processed files ("carbon_pec50", "fullerene_class", "coated_m_pec50", "coated_m_class", "meox_pec50", "meox_class", "metal_pec50" and "metal_class"), description of data and the definition of parameters.

Additional steps of the implementation were columns annotation with parameters definitions and ontology terms, completion of the description and metadata.

The data and associated metadata can be accessed in the EdelweissData at “View datasets” section, by searching “KIT Daphnia data on nanoparticles” and its APIs in JSON format can be reused in an interoperable way. “Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database” is also listed in the OpenRiskNet catalogue and service registry.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

This service was not integrated as a stand-alone database but using pre-existing OpenRiskNet data management solutions. EwC supported KIT’s integration of “Daphnia magna nanotoxicity database” by providing access to the EdelweissData solution, curation of data as well as details and guidance on the preparation steps for upload and annotation.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The Daphnia dataset was not directly used in case studies or workflows but access routes are described in the description of EdelweissData in the DataCure case study.

Nano-QSAR to predict cytotoxicity of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/165/>

Functionality of service

A Nano-QSAR model developed by KIT (Korea Institute of Toxicology) for the prediction of cytotoxicity caused by metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, was integrated into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure through the Jaqpot web platform. The binary classification model was built using the Logistic regression algorithm. The structures involved are metal and metal oxide cluster structures (prepared by Material studio visualizer) and hydroxylated metal ions. The descriptors involved are quantum mechanical descriptors, calculated from MOPAC (PM7). The model has been presented in a publication by Shin et al. [5].

Since quantum mechanical descriptors and molecular structure for the nanoparticle cluster both were prepared by commercial software, here, the model was implemented with descriptors already calculated for numerous metal and metal oxide nanoparticles.

Implementation details

Before the Implementation Challenge, the nano-QSAR model was only available to researchers locally at KIT. To integrate it into OpenRiskNet as a stand-alone service, the full development of a web service with APIs would have been required. To avoid this large effort, it was agreed between KIT and NTUA to use existing general QSAR functionality in the OpenRiskNet service Jaqpot.

NTUA and KIT worked together to transfer the nano-QSAR model into a python notebook that created a web service from the model, exposing it as a REST API hosted in the Jaqpot platform and also over the Jaqpot GUI, as shown in the figure below. It is accessible at <https://ui-jaqpot.prod.openrisknet.org/model/8iHAbHwenOYHnhYmaHYF> (after logging in).

The model has been shared within the OpenRiskNet organisation:

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

Similar to the Daphnia database above, OpenRiskNet and especially the partner NTUA, not only supported the development of the KIT Nano-QSAR REST API services by providing expertise and guidelines, but also provided the generic modelling platform to realise the service. Also the development of the Python workflow to prepare the model for its use in Jaqpot was done with the strong support of NTUA.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The service was integrated into OpenRiskNet in the context of ModelRX case study to demonstrate the generality of the approach described for a blood-brain barrier model in detail in Deliverable D15.

ToxPlanet database

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/157/>

Functionality of service

ToxPlanet aggregates and curates toxicology and chemical hazard information from over 500 sources. Commercial access to the content is provided via a web-based GUI that incorporates searching, retrieval, and display capabilities. ToxPlanet includes the *EXPERTIndex* that includes millions of synonyms including CASRN, InChiKeys, IUPAC names, SMILES, and other common nomenclature to easily locate and retrieve relevant results.

Implementation details

ToxPlanet is made available in OpenRiskNet via a REST API, which relays all queries to the services running on the ToxPlanet platform and provides the corresponding responses to the user.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

The ToxPlanet REST API for services is exposed as an OpenRiskNet service and was developed with the help of EwC. Additionally, guidance for the optimization of the APIs was given by UM and Fraunhofer to allow text-mining applications.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

ToxPlanet is incorporated into the DataCure case study which establishes a process for data curation and annotation that makes use of APIs (eliminating the need for manual file sharing) and semantic annotations for a more systematic and reproducible data curation workflow. Furthermore, ToxPlanet provides part of the toxicological reference data required for the TGX and SysGroup case studies as a proof-of-concept, which will be extended in a follow-up project by ToxPlanet, EwC, Fraunhofer and UM.

OCHEM models

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/154/>

Functionality of service

OCHEM prediction services have been developed by BIGCHEM GmbH and provide access to physico-chemical and toxicity predictions for ten models available at the On-line Chemical Database and Modelling environment (<http://ochem.eu>). The physico-chemical properties include logP, melting point, and water solubility (intrinsic). The biological properties include bio-concentration factor (BCF), hERG classification task, AMES toxicity classification task, and CYP1A2 inhibition classification task. Toxicity prediction in OCHEM includes 29 different types of toxicities. For a majority of models, the predictions are accompanied by estimated accuracy. The models' predictions are available under CC-BY-NC license.

Implementation details

The models implemented as prediction workflows are made available in OpenRiskNet via a REST API developed as part of the Implementation Challenge, which relays all queries to the services running at OCHEM platform and provides the corresponding responses back to the user. This is being implemented in such a manner because some models in OCHEM are proprietary, and although available free for use, are not made open source by OCHEM GmbH. The web interface for the REST API is developed using the Swagger framework and the users can interact with the API using a Swagger UI based frontend in a web browser. In addition, the REST API calls can also be initiated programmatically in case of interacting with the API in a Notebook or scripted program.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

The OCHEM REST API for services running at the On-line Chemical Database and Modelling environment have been exposed in the OpenRiskNet services. The Swagger framework based REST API for OCHEM services was developed with the help of JGU Mainz.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The service was integrated into OpenRiskNet in the context of ModelRX case study to demonstrate the generality of the approach described for a blood-brain barrier model in detail in Deliverable D1.5.

FAME 3 site-of-metabolism predictor

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/145/>

Functionality of service

FAME (FAst MEtabolizer) is a machine learning model for the prediction of sites of metabolism (SOMs) for drug-like and other xenobiotic compounds [6]. FAME 3 predicts SOMs for phase I, phase II or combined phase I/II metabolism. It uses the ExtraTrees machine learning models based on circular 2D atomic descriptors [7]. FAME is currently being used at several large pharmaceutical and agrochemical companies. The main components used are the Chemistry Development Kit (CDK) and WEKA, both of which have been developed in JAVA. FAME has a simple command line interface and produces a simple web page and CSV files as output.

Implementation details

The API specification was developed using the Swagger toolchain, which was also used to generate a template implementation of the service. This way the code is automatically annotated with documentation strings that enable direct user interaction with the API endpoints using a browser-based user Interface (the Swagger UI). In addition, FAME 3 offers a regular browser-based interface designed to be used by human users and also a standalone application (see links in Table 1).

The API enables access to all FAME 3 features as implemented in both the standalone application and the web service. The API accepts submissions of chemical structures in common file formats (SDF files, SMILES strings and combination thereof). API endpoint input and output data exchange are standardised to a machine-readable JSON format and the OpenAPI data type definitions ensure seamless integration of the containerised service in the OpenRiskNet infrastructure and data exchange with other services.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

The implementation was performed by the Implementation Challenge winner supported by VU especially regarding the annotation and interoperability concepts. Furthermore, concepts for the optimization of results from multiple metabolite prediction algorithms were developed in collaboration between University of Hamburg, VU and UU.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The service was integrated in the context of **MetaP** case study and builds a central part of the workflow combining different metabolite prediction mechanisms to obtain results of higher confidence.

Prosilico's Human In Vivo ADME/PK-Prediction Studio

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/152/>

Functionality of service

Prosilico builds predictive QSAR models on high-quality in vivo data to predict the following primary human ADME/PK parameters for chemical compounds:

1. **Fraction absorbed (f_{abs}):** Predicts passive intestinal permeability-based fraction absorbed in-vivo in man (not considering solubility, active transport or instability in GI fluids)
2. **Intrinsic hepatic metabolic clearance (CL_{int}):** Predicts intrinsic hepatic metabolic clearance in-vivo in man (phase I metabolism and conjugation)
3. **Steady-state volume of distribution (V_{ss}):** Predicts steady-state volume of distribution in-vivo in man (not considering enterohepatic circulation)
4. **Fraction unbound in human plasma (f_u):** Predicts in-vitro fraction unbound in human plasma.
5. **Maximum in-vivo solubility/dissolution potential (f_{diss}):** Predicts the maximum solubility/dissolution potential in the human gastrointestinal tract in-vivo following oral dosing.

The following secondary human ADME/PK parameters are then calculated based on the 5 primary parameters:

1. **Hepatic clearance (CL_H):** Calculated based on predicted CL_{int} and f_u, hepatic blood flow (1500 mL/min) and the well-stirred liver model.
2. **Oral bioavailability (F):** Calculated based on predicted f_{abs} (not considering active transport or gut-wall metabolism), f_{diss} and CL_H.
3. **Half-life (t₂):** Calculated based on predicted CL_H and V_{ss} (not considering excretion or enterohepatic circulation).

Implementation details

ProSilico models make use of Conformal Prediction methodology that outputs valid prediction intervals at user-specified levels of confidence. We wrapped all ProSilico models using a web-based API developed using Swagger/OpenAPI available from the endpoint <http://prosilico.prod.openrisknet.org>. It delivers results in JSON format.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

The implementation was performed by Prosilico supported by UU with the goal to allow usage of all predictive models from all partners (consortium as well as associated) according to the approach outlined in the ModelRX case study.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

An example Notebook for consuming the Prosilico service inside OpenRiskNet is available at: <https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/notebooks/blob/master/prosilico/prosilico-orn.ipynb>

Nanoinformatics Tool for the Virtual Screening of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles via Enalos Platform

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/151/>

Functionality of service

The Enalos Nano-QSAR models developed by Novamechanics are made available in OpenRiskNet by being exposed at <https://model-nova-mech.prod.openrisknet.org/novamechanics/swagger-ui.html>. The user receives feedback from the service as predictions which are characterised as *active/inactive* along with an indication of its reliability based on the model's domain of applicability limits. A screenshot of the results in the Swagger documentation is provided below:

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for a REST API endpoint. It includes the following sections:

- Curl:** A command to perform a POST request with headers for Content-Type (multipart/form-data) and Accept (application/json), and a body of type formData.
- Request URL:** The endpoint path: `https://model-nova-mech.prod.openrisknet.org:443/novamechanics/QNAR_IronOxide_Toxicity_uploadFile`.
- Request Headers:** A JSON object containing `"Accept": "*/*"`.
- Response Body:** A JSON array of four objects, each representing a prediction result. Each object contains:
 - `"domain": "reliable"`
 - `"prediction": "\"inactive\""`
 - `"rowID": "\"Row0\""` (for the first row), `"Row1\""`, `"Row2\""`, and `"Row3\""` for the subsequent rows.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

The Enalos Metal Oxide nanoparticles virtual screening REST API services are exposed in the OpenRiskNet services and were developed with the support of NTUA especially with respect to the requirements for QSAR models to allow for a strong interlinking of different services.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The service was integrated into OpenRiskNet in the context of ModelRX case study as a demonstration for the generalization of the guidelines for interoperable QSAR workflows.

nanoQSAR model for the prediction of the cellular uptake and the virtual screening of nanoparticles via Enalos Platform

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/150/>

Functionality of service

A validated predictive model for nanoparticles cellular uptake, that is part of NovaMechanics' Enalos infrastructure deployed into the OpenRiskNet reference environment. The model can be used for the predictions of cellular uptake for new structures that are imported into the server via sdf format.

Implementation details

Enalos Nano-QSAR models are made available in OpenRiskNet by being exposed as a REST API at <https://model-nova-mech.prod.openrisknet.org/novamechanics/swagger-ui.html>. The user is provided with a predicted cellular uptake value in log₁₀[NP] (pM)/cell for each structure entered, and an indication of whether this prediction could be considered reliable based on the domain of applicability of the model. A screenshot of the results in the Swagger documentation is provided below:

```
Curl
curl -X POST --header 'Content-Type: multipart/form-data' --header 'Accept: application/json' {"type":"formData"} 'https://model-nova-mech.prod.openrisknet.org:443/novamechanics/QNAR_PaCa2_uploadFile'

Request URL
https://model-nova-mech.prod.openrisknet.org:443/novamechanics/QNAR_PaCa2_uploadFile

Request Headers
{
  "Accept": "*/*"
}

Response Body
[
  {
    "domain": "reliable",
    "molID": "1",
    "paCa_Cellular_Uptake": 3.7950000000000004
  }
]

Response Code
```

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

In the same way as the Nanoinformatics Tool for the Virtual Screening of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles service described above, the Enalos nanoQSAR model REST API services are exposed in the OpenRiskNet services and were developed with the help of NTUA.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The service was integrated into OpenRiskNet in the context of ModelRX case study.

PySquonk

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/167/>

Functionality of service

PySquonk is a Python client for the Squonk Jobexecutor REST API. This API allows to programmatically execute the same services that are accessible through the Squonk Computational Notebook. This was of interest to Diamond Light Source as they wished to invoke these services from their Fragalysis (<https://fragalysis.diamond.ac.uk/>) application that is part of their fragment screening program. The appserver tier of Fragalysis is a Python Django application so the PySquonk Python client would facilitate this integration.

An example would be to take a fragment screening hit (XRay crystal structure of a fragment in its target) and then invoke Squonk services to expand out that molecule to related molecules and then to perform virtual screening using docking and then run ADMET predictions of the candidate compounds.

Implementation details

The PySquonk client was created and can be found in this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/InformaticsMatters/pysquonk>. Included are:

- Python modules with the PySquonk Python code
- Test data [\[here\]](#)
- Sample service configurations (YAML files) [\[here\]](#)
- Test scripts
- Basic documentation on usage
- API documentation [\[here\]](#)
- Jupyter notebooks exemplifying usage [\[here\]](#)

The PySquonk modules have been published to PyPi as the module named im-pysquonk, the Python Package Index, from where they can easily be pulled into any Python environment and used.

This project was successfully completed and is now ready for use at Diamond Light Source and other environments wanting to access Squonk services. These Squonk services could be running on the OpenRiskNet reference environment or and other OpenRiskNet Virtual Environment (VE). Authentication is typically needed through the Keycloak SSO environment running in the VE.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

Even if the project was proposed by Diamond Light Source and the Implementation Challenge was also awarded to them, the needed manpower to realize the implementation could not be provided by Diamond Light Source during the runtime of the OpenRiskNet project. To be able to still provide the services, which provides optimized ways to link in-house workflows with OpenRiskNet services, the work was performed at the OpenRiskNet partner IM with the scientific and technical supervision by Diamond Light Source.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

This service was not used in a case study but for different workflows inside Diamond Light Source provided to their users.

ToxicoDB

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/153/>

Functionality of service

ToxicoDB is a web application to mine large and small scale toxicogenomics datasets. To better understand the molecular mechanisms underlying compound toxicity, great efforts have been made in screening of drugs/chemicals by various groups to generate datasets such as Open-TG GATEs and DrugMatrix. The inspiration for this application comes from the need for a common ground for analyzing toxicogenomics datasets with maximum overlap and consistency. The ToxicoDB will provide an intuitive interface for all users (including users that are not computer-savvy) to mine the complex toxicogenomic data.

Implementation details

ToxicoDB is implemented using NodeJS/ExpressJS for the backend with a MySQL database and ReactJS as well as d3.js and Plotly.js for the frontend. The built-in API can be queried at <http://www.toxicodb.ca/api> and provides all the data contained in the ToxicoDB database. An R package (ToxicoGx) to analyze toxicogenomics datasets is also available to download from CRAN (<https://cran.r-project.org/package=ToxicoGx>).

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

Toxicogenomics datasets compiled by the consortium are undergoing integration into ToxicoDB. ASAT-db [8], compiled by UM will be linked to the web app for increased coverage of drug annotations. Increased visibility of the database and the curation efforts of the OpenRiskNet, as well as facilitating access to toxicogenomic data and analytical tools to the whole scientific community is achieved via the OpenRiskNet catalogue as well as the listing of OpenRiskNet services in eInfraCentral and EOSC marketplace.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

ToxicoDB's toxicological data and toxicogenomics datasets are an important source of information in the TGX and SysGroup case studies. Furthermore, ToxicoDB provides more general toxicological information for the DataCure case study.

ToxTargetLinks

Description in OpenRiskNet service catalogue

<https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/166/>

Functionality of service

ToxTargetLink implements methods for extending rare disease networks with data and knowledge on toxic compounds (especially toxic drugs) that may affect the network (i.e. hit a protein target present in the network) and thus might affect disease development. Originally, the information on the toxic molecular initiating drug-target interactions was planned to be taken from the OpenRiskNet platform, but initial investigations showed that further external data sources were required. We have identified the CTD database (Comparative Toxicogenomic Database) as a suitable data source and have developed a prototype showing its integration. The prototype motivates the future integration of such a resource to the OpenRiskNet platform.

Implementation details

CTD database downloads are parsed and transformed into the XGMML linkset format for the CyTargetLinker app, by extending the CyTargetLinker external parser. CyTargetLinker is a Cytoscape app that can be used to extend biological networks with regulatory and drug-target interactions.

Specific support offered by OpenRiskNet consortium members

UM gave support with the CyTargetLinker application, linkset development, and the definition of API requirements for future developments that would allow CyTargetlinker to ingest data from more generic API calls.

Integration into case studies and example workflows

The functionality was demonstrated using the example rare disease networks. During the EJP workshop in Maastricht in November 2019 more prototype rare disease networks based on rare disease pathways were developed that were already present on the WikiPathways rare disease portal using the Cytoscape WikiPathways App. These prototype rare disease networks are being further extended using CyTargetLinker with the new CTD linkset. The approach is complementary to an approach based on the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) use case. For that, European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP RD) wants to use, yet to be developed, molecular versions of AOPs and look at the overlap with rare disease networks. Since we expect the type of toxic compound interactions that we addressed in this Implementation Challenge to work via initiating events that hit targets in rare disease networks, these networks are expected to also have an overlap with AOPs where that interaction is the molecular initiating event. The two approaches are therefore expected to give related insights in the biological interactions leading to adverse effects influencing the rare disease process.

Participation of the associate partners at the final OpenRiskNet workshop

All implementation challenge winners were invited to give a presentation on their services during the final OpenRiskNet workshop, which took place in Amsterdam on 23-24 October 2019. More details on the workshop are given in the Deliverable Report D3.5 “Dissemination & Training Activities (Final Report)”. Travel costs to the meeting were reimbursed as part of the Implementation Challenge budget. Based on an excellent response, we were able to allocate the full morning of the second day of the workshop to presentations of Implementation Challenge winners. It started with five scientific talks from four of the Implementation Challenge winners and also one associated partner (SIB) not funded under the programme:

- **Urban Fagerholm (Prosilico, Sweden):** Strategy used to build confidence in PROSILICO's in silico methods for prediction of human clinical ADME/PK
- **Johannes Kirchmair (University of Hamburg, Germany):** FAME 3: Predicting the Sites of Metabolism in Small Molecules for Phase 1 and Phase 2 Metabolic Enzymes and FAME 3 API in OpenRiskNet
- **Lydie Lane (CALIPHO group, SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Switzerland):** Using SPARQL to explore human protein data in neXtProt and beyond
- **Sisira Kadambat Nair (Princess Margaret Cancer Centre, University Health Network, Toronto, Canada):** ToxicGx: An R platform for integrated toxicogenomics data analysis
- **Holly M. Mortensen (US Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Research and Development, USA):** US EPA AOP-DB: A database resource for the exploration of Adverse Outcome Pathways

This was followed by a demonstration given by **Matt Timberlake (ToxPlanet, USA)** on their ToxPlanet, a knowledge resource for risk assessors and regulators providing access to more than 9 million chemical specific documents. Another highlight was the presentation on the first external OpenRiskNet Virtual Environment” given by Tim Dudgeon on behalf of **Diamond Light Source**. As already described above, Diamond Light Source already supported OpenRiskNet during the proposal writing stage and became one of the first associated partners. After the infrastructure matured to a stage where it could be deployed on production cloud systems, Diamond Light Source ported their Fragalysis platform for fragment screening using high-throughput crystallography onto the OpenRiskNet infrastructure and used the first external Virtual Environment to manage their internal workflows. Finally, they applied in the second phase to the Implementation Challenge and the implementation of their tool PySquonk was funded and executed in collaboration with IM. In this way, they went through all possible stages of associated partnership from early supporter to early adopter to administrator and user of a VE to finally a service provider and Implementation Challenge winner.

CONCLUSION

The Implementation Challenge was able to achieve its goal to bring in third-party applications into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure. In total, 10 institutions including Universities, SMEs as well as Governmental and Regulatory Agencies were selected by the Scientific Advisory Board and the integration of 12 services was supported financially and technically by the OpenRiskNet consortium. These services cover data and information sources as well as different software tools from all risk assessment areas and are complementing the services provided by the OpenRiskNet consortium. The third-party services were highlighted at the final OpenRiskNet workshop demonstrating the generality of the OpenRiskNet approaches and infrastructure to support all data and software services developed in the toxicology and risk assessment community and beyond. Continuing development and usage of OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure in other research and infrastructure projects and the community in general will bring in additional services providing a complete coverage of the diverse tasks of risk assessment and expanding to related, neighboring applications fields.

GLOSSARY

The list of terms or abbreviations with the definitions, used in the context of OpenRiskNet project and the e-infrastructure development is available:

<https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki/Glossary>

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ANNEXES

Annex 1. Application form to the implementation challenge

Application for implementation challenge

Implementation Challenge was created to select external tools especially in areas of risk assessment not completely covered by the OpenRiskNet consortium for prioritized integration partial financially and strongly technically supported by researchers of OpenRiskNet partners.

Similar to the internal services, these funds and the technical support will cover the work associated with making the service OpenRiskNet compliant. This includes the adoption of the OpenRiskNet API concept including the interoperability layer, generation of the data schemata for in- and output as well as the containerization for deployment.

To apply, please fill in this form to propose up to 5 data sources or software tools from your group to be considered in the challenge. Please give enough details so that the selection committee can evaluate the amount of work and funding necessary for integration.

Please find a preview of all the questions here: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1vYqKRuoAUUCjZ_YJJsEMGnXs2quyb7sg. We hope that this convince you that we are not asking for much of your time.

* Required

1. **Before you can continue with this form, you need to agree with OpenRiskNet Privacy Policy:** <https://openrisknet.org/privacy-policy/> *

Check all that apply.

I agree with the Privacy Policy

2. **First name ***

3. **Last name ***

4. **Institution ***

5. **E-mail ***

Service description

Up to 5 services (databases and analysis/modelling tools) per applicant can be proposed for the implementation challenge.

6. **Name of service ***

7. Risk assessment area *

Check all that apply.

- Toxicology database
- Physicochemical properties database
- Bioassay database
- Omics database
- Knowledge base and data mining
- Identifier conversion and metasearch
- Data analysis and processing
- Hazard prediction
- Metabolism prediction
- Bioinformatics and omics analysis
- Read across and grouping
- AOP related tools
- Biokinetics
- Other: _____

8. Please describe the service including answers to the following questions: 1) How will your service profit from OpenRiskNet and specifically from combining it with other OpenRiskNet services? 2) How will other services or the core infrastructure profit from the integration of your service? 3) To which OpenRiskNet case studies you service could be applied? 4) Will the service be used directly by scientists, risk assessors or regulators or will it support the core infrastructure by providing features to many services (e.g. ontologies, file format validation, etc.)? *

9. Additional information available at (e.g. links to homepage, user manual and support) *

10. Publications

11. Implementation status

Check all that apply.

- Available as web service
- Graphical user interface available
- Application programming interface available
- Containerized

12. Targeted users (1) *

Mark only one oval.

- End user (easy to use without programming skills)
- Developer (programming or scripting know-how needed e.g. for workflow development)

13. Targeted users (2) *

Check all that apply.

- Academic researchers
- Industry researchers
- Risk assessors
- Regulators
- Informed public
- Other: _____

14. Licence *

Mark only one oval.

- Open source
- Freeware
- Commercial license

15. *

Mark only one oval.

- More services
- Submit application *Stop filling out this form.*

Service description

Up to 5 services (databases and analysis/modelling tools) per applicant can be proposed for the implementation challenge.

16. Name of service *
